

THE ROLE OF THE MONETARY POLICY IN ECONOMIC GROWTH

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Abstract: The article examines main objectives of the macroeconomic policy by dividing them into internal and external balance. Furthermore, provides basic explanation of how monetary policy can affect long-run economic growth of an economy by ensuring mitigation of the short-run fluctuations.

Key words: macroeconomic policy, monetary policy, long-rung growth, short-run fluctuation, internal balance, external balance.

Introduction

Improving the living standards of the nation today remains the main goal of the socio-economic policy of all modern societies. In this turn, it should be noted that the most important aspect of prosperity is undoubtedly economic growth.

In the last few decades, economic views have increasingly focused on the importance of socio-economic development which is characterized to what extent economic growth is inclusive, rather than just overall growth of the economy over time. To achieve these objectives scientists all over the world has been striving to find optimal policies, which enables governments the accelerate welfare without undermining key principles of the market economy.

Thus, over a century period there have been developed different theories upon which countries have been to developing and implementing their macroeconomic policies. In fact, one of the such theories that started come to existence as the major macroeconomic policy choices is monetary policy alongside with fiscal policy.

In particular, monetary policy, in addition to providing the state with the necessary resources for the creation of social goods, maintain stability in the economy by curbing the inflationary pressure that occurs in the process of development, redistribute income, stimulate the development of small, medium and large industrial and agricultural enterprises with the help of incentivized loans, as well as is widely used to achieve necessary social goals. However, results of these practices were different in different countries depending on which theories and to what extend were applied, and in what stages of the economic growth they were practiced.

To understand the reasons behind the above-mentioned different scenarios, it is necessary, first examine nature and implications of monetary policy in relation with the objectives of the modern economy.

In general, in any open economy governments concern mainly about the internal and external balance condition. In other words, internal balance necessitates the full utilization of a country`s resources (full employment) as well as stability of price in the country. External balance is achieved when a country`s current account is neither so heavily in deficit that it may be unable to repay its foreign debts in the future, nor so heavily in surplus that foreigners are put in that position.

In this perspective main macroeconomic objectives of the policy-makers is attempt to accomplish long-run economic growth, while ensuring short-run stability in different stages

of the business cycle. Thus, the primary macroeconomic goals in this context are to analyze the structure and performance of national economy, as well as the policy initiatives that policymakers employ to attempt to influence long-run economic performance of the country by reducing fluctuations over the business cycle.

Graphically, these two growth phenomena can be illustrated as follows (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Long-run economic growth and short-run fluctuations (business cycle pattern)

As it is mentioned above, one of the main objectives of the government is to achieve long-run economic growth, which is defined by *Growth Trend Line* (straight line) in Figure 1. There are various theories that tries to explain how a country can achieve this level. Here arises one of the macroeconomics issues of what determines nation's long-run economic growth?

Another aspect of the business cycle is short-run fluctuations which reflects short-term in-equilibrium between supply and demand which leads economy to be in a boom or recession.

Although there are different theories and views on what determines economic growth, most of them consider GDP as the main indicator of economic growth. GDP growth rate is the level of created value added within the country, which in turn, determines the level of economic growth. Thus, the process of economic growth is mainly based on the introduction of new products and new production technology, capital accumulation, investments in physical and human capital, as well as the implementation of new production processes. Economic growth, in turn, is the basis for improving the well-being of the nation. However, various reasons are given regarding the factors that accommodate economic growth.

Role of the monetary policy long-run economic growth and short-run fluctuation's in economy is that, Central bank by increasing (expansionary policy) and decreasing (contractionary policy) money supply can affect saving behavior of the consumers, thereby creating basis for investment which then enables country to growth over a long period of time. Meanwhile, this policy also ensures mitigating large fluctuation's in the short-run in order to prevent economy from being in economic boom and economic recession for a long period of time.

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